

Subject: Invitation for companies to be part of the INDUSAC project

Dear Sir or Madam,

On behalf of Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley and the INDUSAC project, we would like to invite your organisation to participate in an exciting new project aimed at strengthening the collaboration between industry and academia.

INDUSAC is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to develop and validate an Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism. Within the project, we will facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows the development of solutions that address the needs and interests of companies in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries¹.

Companies are invited to register on the platform and prepare a **non-confidential summary of a challenge** they might be facing. The Challenge may be from nine general areas: (1) Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow, (2) Finding white spots in the product portfolio, (3) Marketing campaign of the future, (4) Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis, (5) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona), (6) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios), (7) Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning, (8) Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain, and (9) Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system) (for details see the Appendix).

Selected international co-creation teams comprising 3-6 students and/or researchers will solve the companies' challenges within 4-8 weeks. The company does not have any financial obligations or commitments towards the co-creation team. INDUSAC has a budget of 900.000 EUR gross intended for student members of co-creation teams, where mini-grants of 3.000 EUR gross will be distributed among student members of each team.

By participating in the project company receives a solution to its challenge, gets an opportunity to meet young bright minds from across Europe to consider as future collaborators or employees, and increases its own visibility through international collaboration.

Timeline:

- [INDUSAC platform](#) for posting the company's challenges open in November 2023
- Motivation Letters submitted by the co-creation teams in February 2024
- engagement from the company to guide the co-creation team foreseen for March & April 2024
- results from the co-creation team will be available in May 2024.

Two later cut-off dates for receiving new motivation letters will be available for new challenges. It is thus advisable that the challenges are relevant for a reasonable period of time.

We would be happy to provide you with more information about the project and its goals. If you are interested in learning more, please do not hesitate to contact us or visit the website www.indusac.eu.

Yours sincerely,

Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

¹ Widening and associated countries: Widening countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia; [source](#)) and Associated Countries (1. Albania, 2. Armenia, 3. Bosnia and Herzegovina, 4. Faroe Islands, 5. Georgia, 6. Iceland, 7. Israel, 8. Kosovo, 9. Moldova, 10. Montenegro, 11. North Macedonia, 12. Norway, 13. Serbia, 14. Tunisia, 15. Turkey, 16. Ukraine, 17. UK).

Appendix: What kind of results can a company expect by posting a particular Challenge

Type of Challenge	Result to expect
Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario/trend analysis and references (e.g. Word) • Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g. Excel)
Finding white spots in the product portfolio Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic analysis of product portfolio (e.g. BCG-matrix) • Clustering of product portfolio (e.g. PowerPoint) • Action-plan /white spot analysis for relevant clusters
Marketing campaign of the future Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market analysis with a focus on customers • Trend analysis combining future customers and marketing trends • Design of a marketing campaign
Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market analysis to define the platform • Digital Platform prototype (click dummy) (based on existing product profiles)
Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona) Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persona • Product Profile • Service/ Product idea
Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios) Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persona • Product Profile • Service/ Product idea
Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SWOT-Analysis • Business plan • Estimation of profitability
Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of alternative product ideas • Utility analysis and evaluation of ideas • Virtual prototype
Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS The development of new business models for a given product.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persona (user behaviour) • Business model • 3 alternatives and subsequent utility analysis